

MACHINING OF FIBRE REINFORCED MATERIALS WITH
LASER BEAM: CUT QUALITY EVALUATION

V. Tagliaferri, I. Crivelli Visconti
Dipartimento di Ingegneria dei Materiali e della
Produzione, Università di Napoli,
80125 Napoli,
ITALY

and

A. Di Ilio
Dipartimento di Energetica
Università di L'Aquila,
Monteluco Royo L'Aquila,
ITALY

ABSTRACT

Experimental results obtained by laser machining of different fibre reinforced plastics are reported. A criterion to evaluate laser cutting quality for FRP is proposed and the influence of cutting variables on some of cutting quality parameters has been investigated. In the range of values of the experimental parameters used in the research the cut quality is strongly dependent on the cutting speed and laser beam energy distribution.

INTRODUCTION

The use of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) normally permits to obtain a product in its final shape in order to reduce machining to a minimum [1,2]. However the actual tendency to introduce composites in mass production, like in the automotive industry, will at least partially reintroduce the necessity of machining, such as cutting and drilling. These operations can be performed by three principal ways: modified conventional tools, laser beam and water-jet [3,5].

Whatever the technology employed, it is very important to identify the correlation from cut quality and cutting parameters. Generally the cut quality is strongly dependent on cutting mechanism and material properties [2]. In a previous works [5-7] we have studied the influence of thermal properties on the laser performances in FRP cutting. It was noticed that the cut quality both as uniformity of the surface morphology and low roughness, was better in presence of low differences in thermal properties

between constituent materials.

In this work we try to identify the cut quality parameters observed in laser machining of different FRP and to correlate them with cutting parameters such as beam power, cutting speed and gas flow.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Interrupted cuts were performed on 50x100 mm² FRP laminates of different thickness with a 2.0 kW cw CO₂ laser. In tab. I geometry and constituent materials of FRP and cutting parameters are reported. The laminates were made with a ratio way to weight equal to one and the fibre volume fraction was about 0.5. FRP were cut with a values of beam power between 0.8 and 2.0 kW; this choice was made on results of previous investigations [6,7] for that value of the beam power was able to cut different FRP 2-5 mm thick at high speed. The laser beam, with Gaussian distribution of energy, was focused into the surface of the laminates by a lens of 63.3 mm. The focal spot diameter was about of 0.5 mm and medium value power density was about 10⁶ W/cm². An inert gas jet, coaxial with the laser beam, impinged orthogonally on the laminates through a 2 mm diameter nozzle to avoid burnings. Four values of gas flow were employed. On each laminates six interrupted cuts were carried out parallel to warp direction with different values of feed speed (0.5-13 m/min). The feed was achieved by a numerical controlled table. On each cut the following measurements were made: cut path width, cut surface examination at low magnification, evaluation of the heat affected zone, kerf geometry and surface examination by SEM. The measurements carried out allow to evaluate the cut quality parameters that we assume to be important in FRP laser machining.

TABLES I

Composites constituents materials, geometry and cutting parameters.

Composites	S (mm)	V (m/min)	P (kW)	Ø (l/min)
Aramidic Polyester	2.0+4.5	0.5+13	0.8+2.0	88+100
Graphite Polyester	2.0+5.0	0.5+9.0	0.8+2.0	88+100
Glass Polyester	2.0+3.5	0.5+9.0	0.8+2.0	88+100

S = thickness, V = cutting velocity, P = beam power, Ø gas flow.

CUT QUALITY PARAMETERS

In previous works it was observed that the morphology of the FRP cut edge is characterized by fibres pultruded by the matrix surrounded by large zones with loss of material [5-7]. The kerf width is not constant and a slope of the cut surface is evident. The presence of charred materials

(resin and fibres) has been observed and in some few cases delamination zones were present. On the basis of experimental and theoretical results obtained we have then identified the principal quality criteria as reported in fig. 1. The quality parameters adopted thus are:

- The kerf width at inlet (W_i) and outlet (W_o) of laser beam.
- The heat affected zone size (W_d); this zone is characterized by the presence of fibres debonded from the matrix (or matrix recession) and thermal degradation of the fibres and matrix. The heat affected zone is to be assumed as a zone where regular transfer of load from matrix to fibres does not occur.
- The slope of cut surface.
- The delamination extension.
- The presence of charred materials.

Among the many various cutting parameters which influence the cut quality cutting speed, laser power and gas flow have been chosen as the most important ones and their effects on same cut quality variable were tested in detail.

Fig. 1 - Terminology of quality for FRP laser beam cutting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Aramid and Glass FRP

Kerf width. Typical aspects of kerf obtained at different cutting speed are shown in fig. 2 a,b,c (AFRP) ; similar aspects are evident in GFRP. It can be observed that as the cutting speed increases the kerf width and slope of the cut surfaces change. It is not evident the presence of fibres or charred material in the kerf even at the maximum cutting speed to obtain through cuts. Fig. 3 shows W_i and W_o vs. cutting speed and beam power for the different composites analyzed. Both the values of W_i and W_o decrease as the cutting speed increases and it is evident the presence of a cutting speed value up to which both W_i and W_o are almost constant. The W_i "limit"

values is about the laser spot beam diameter. The kerf width at the outlet of the laser beam tend to zero. The W_i and W_o values seem to be less sensitive to the power changes. These results suggest that the modification of the kerf width depends on the interaction time between laser beam and material, i.e. the mass of removed material depends directly on the amount of energy input ($E=Pxt_i$). In composites the mechanism of material removal depends on the thermal properties of the constituents and, moreover the fibres require higher amount of energy with respect to the matrix; this fact is evidenced in fig 3 where the value of removed material per unit length of cut (evaluated as $W_i+W_o/2xS$) is larger in the case of aramidic fibres for the same power and cutting speed condition. W_i and W_o values are not influenced by the gas jet flow, fig. 4.

Fig. 2 - Typical aspect of kerf at different cutting speed: a) $V=3.5\text{m/min}$; b) $V=5\text{m/min}$; c) $V=7\text{m/min}$; d) $V=11\text{m/min}$. AFRP, $S=3\text{mm}$, $P=800\text{ W}$.

Fig. 3 - Width of the kerf at the inlet (W_i) and outlet (W_o) of the laser beam versus cutting speed and beam power.

Fig. 4 - W_i and W_o vs. gas jet flow; AFRP, $S=2\text{mm}$, $P=800\text{ W}$, $V=7\text{m/min}$.

Slope of the cut surface. Fig 5 shows the results of $\text{tg}\alpha$ evaluation in various conditions of cutting speed and thickness. These results indicate that the cut quality is better at a medium value of the cutting speed ($V=5\text{m/min}$) for each thickness analyzed. Furthermore as the thickness decreases the optimum speed increases gradually and the corresponding range of constant quality enlarges. The absolute value of $\text{tg}\alpha$ decreases as the thickness increases.

Fig. 5 - Slope of the cut surfaces vs. cutting speed for AFRP laminates with different thickness; $P=800\text{ W}$.

The cut path shape can be a result of the distribution of energy within the laser spot, that generally follows a Gaussian law (TEM 00), and the energy absorption through the thickness. At the distance r from the axis of the beam, the balance between the energy input and the amount of energy required to vaporize the material is [8]:

$$I_0 \exp(-2r^2/d^2) \cdot 2\pi r \, dr = Z \cdot 2 \, rd \cdot C \quad (1)$$

where: I_0 is the maximum intensity of the beam energy; d is the beam diameter conventionally measured to the point where the beam has decreased to $1/e^2$ of I_0 ; Z is the depth of removed material; $C = \rho\lambda$ is the specific energy required to vaporize the material [7]. The hypothesis under which eq.1 holds is that the losses of energy for conduction through the cut surfaces and shielding effects of the vapour on the laser beam are negligible. These considerations are particularly true for composites with aramidic and glass fibres which exhibit low thermal diffusivity. However it must be observed that the presence of a melted state in glass fibre is neglected.

From eq. 1 the profile of the cut surface can be evaluated as:

$$Z = 1/C \cdot I_0 \exp(-2r^2/d^2) \quad (2)$$

Therefore the cut path can be seen theoretically as a profile with a Gaussian trend.

If we consider that the spot translates with a velocity V , the distribution of the energy that impinges on the surface of the material can be expressed as:

$$E(r) = \int_0^{t_i} I_0 \exp(-2r^2/d^2) \, dt$$

where:

$$r = (d^2/4 + V^2 t^2 - 2Vt(d^2/4 - a^2))^{.5}$$

V is the cutting speed and t_i is the interaction time.

As the cutting speed increases $E(r)$ tends to diminish up to a minimum value sufficient to vaporize the material through the thickness to obtain a cut-off. Moreover, it must be observed that the interaction zone, in which the energy is sufficient to vaporize the material, between the beam and material tend to become narrower (figs.2 and 3). In fig. 6 the modification of $\tan \alpha$ as a function of the cutting speed is schematically represented according to the previous observations. As it can be seen, the zone of the energy Gaussian distribution actually employed for cutting changes as the cutting speed increases; consequently, the kerf path changes showing a minimum value at an intermediate value of speed. These considerations may explain the experimental results reported in fig.5. A simple correlation between the cut path behaviour observed in the experimental samples and the theoretical consideration is not possible for the presence of shielding effects due to the vaporized material within the kerf which reduces the energy absorbed by the material.

Heat affected zone. In fig. 7 the values of the heat affected zone size (W_d) at the inlet of the beam are reported vs. cutting speed. As it can be seen the damage in the material tends to reduce with speed. In a previous paper

Fig. 6 - Modification of $\text{tg}\alpha$ as a function of the cutting speed according to theoretical considerations.

Fig. 7 - Values of the heat affected zone sizes (W_d) at the inlet of the beam vs. cutting speed; aramidic and glass FRP; $P=800$ W.

[6], this behaviour has been correlated to the interaction time and thermal properties of the material by using a thermal model of degradation. The thermal damage is lower for composites made with components presenting similar values of both vaporization temperature and thermal diffusivity, as aramidic fibres/polyesters. Moreover the damage diminishes when the energy input is lower due to a shorter interaction time or a lower power level. This fact is particularly evident for glass FRP as it can be observed in fig. 8. The size of W_d is also influenced by the gas jet flow as fig. 9 shows for AFRP; this trend is due to the more cooling efficiency of the gas jet.

Fig. 8 - W_d as a function of laser beam power for GFRP.

Fig. 9 - W_d vs. the gas jet flow for AFRP; $S=2\text{mm}$; $P=800\text{ W}$; $V=7\text{m/min}$.

Graphite Reinforced Plastics

Due to the highly different vaporization temperature between graphite fibres and matrix resin the cut quality of carbon FRP obtained with a cw CO_2 laser is poor. Infact the energy required to cut the composite which is essentially that necessary to vaporize the fibres, is so high, due also to the high thermal diffusivity, that it determines an excessive amount of heat flow into the matrix and therefore a large volume of vaporized resin[7]. Besides, the vaporization of a large quantity of matrix in a very short time

causes a local high pressure peak that produce mechanical damaging (delamination) within the composite.

CONCLUSION

A criterion to evaluate laser cutting quality for fibre reinforced plastics has been attempted. The influence of cutting variables on some of cutting quality parameters has been investigated. The principal factors seem to be the interaction time, and therefore the cutting speed, and the energy distribution accros the laser beam. The former, for a given laser power, determines the amount of heat flow into the material and consequently the size both of the kerf and heat affected zone. The latter influences the slope of the cut surfaces. Moreover, the cut quality is strongly dependent on the thermal properties of the constituents as it was already been observed in previous investigations.

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